

The Crucial Role Played By Big Data Analytics In Enhancing The User Experience Towards E-Learning

R.Vanitha¹, Dr.S.R.Swarnalatha²

¹Assistant professor, Selvam College of Technology, Namakkal.

²Professor & Head, Patel Institute of Science and Management, Bangalore.

Corresponding author- R.Vanitha

Email- rvanithame@gmail.com

Abstract

Today's students and teachers have access to a variety of information because of the adoption of learning management systems (LMS). As the educational system advanced, there was an increase in the total number of pupils enrolled in schools. In recent years, an increasing number of individuals have chosen to get their education via independent study at a distance. Every participant in the educational system, including instructors and students, has a propensity to adjust their practises so that they are in line with the prevailing pedagogical paradigm. As a consequence of this, educational institutions have the obligation to modernise the administrative models and data infrastructures at their institutions in order to improve the effectiveness of their student services and the overall quality of such services. Due to a lack of data storage and analytics capabilities for huge datasets, the enormous volumes of data created by students had to be taken into account and prioritised while creating the educational system. This was necessary because of the lack of capacity for such capabilities. This is one method of analysing the data stored in the LMS. There is a mountain of data to process, and we have a lot of analytical tools at our disposal to help us do so. These insights may then be put to use in the classroom. Developments in cutting-edge technology such as big data analytics have made possible one of the analytical techniques that may be used to find solutions to these difficulties.

Keywords: Big data analytics, E-Learning, User experience

Introduction

The progression of technology may be responsible for the rise in the amount of data stored. The quantity of data that is being produced in today's world is without precedent. In this day and age of digital technology, information is exchanged throughout all departments of a firm, including the department that is responsible for training. The availability and transfer of data through a digital network have contributed to a considerable rise in the amount of the data that is being used. The World Wide Web, mobile devices, and social media are the primary sources of the overwhelming bulk of this data deluge. This enormous quantity of data is referred to as "Big Data" since typical database management solutions are unable to efficiently record, search, store, transmit, manage, visualise, distribute, query, analyse, update, or protect the information for vast datasets.

A. Restrictions Placed on Our Capacity the amount of data generated may be measured in zettabytes, petabytes, and tens of terabytes, respectively. The sheer volume of newly created or repurposed content for use in the classroom 8. The record size of the learning management system or the quantity of information that can be stored by the system the capability of both the system and the organisation to handle and manage data is one of the aspects that must be given the utmost importance. Velocity the rate at which new data is being produced is referred to as "data velocity and it is a term that has its own dedicated noun. As can be observed, the rate at which new information is being collected is accelerating at a dizzyingly rapid rate. It

is difficult to get one's head around the vast quantity of brand-new digital information that is being created. It is directly related to the amount; the more data there is to analyse, the longer it will take. The speed goes up as more and more data is produced and sent. The Characteristic C Not just text files but also audio, video, and picture files are evaluated using this measure. There are numerous different formats in which information may be found, some of which are more organised than others. The aforementioned three dimensions are not the only ones available; there is also a fourth one. A great deal of attention has been paid by data scientists to value as well as variability. For instance, in order to ensure the veracity of big data and the potential use of it, one must deal with the volume, velocity, and diversity of the data. Capability to Undergo Changes Not only is large amounts of information dispersed in ways that are unexpected, but the quality of this information varies greatly. The dissemination of data is influenced by a variety of different factors. Dealing with data loads that are prone to significant fluctuations is a very difficult experience. Because there is such a vast volume of varied and unstructured data, more effort must be put into the analysis. Value It is essential to have an understanding of the "fifth V" in order to comprehend the pattern or behaviour of the data. Because of this, it is possible to develop models that may be used to make predictions. Evidently, the growth of technology for e-learning has made them indispensable for the spread of information. You will have a clearer idea of how your students' education as a whole is progressing as a result of

using the LMS to gather extensive information on your students' usage of any device to which they have access. This will assist you to better meet your students' needs and provide for their care. The value of the LMS is being recognised by a significant number of countries, and those nations are working hard to enhance their educational systems in order to better satisfy the requirements of their own populations. They are mining the data from the institutions in order to construct intelligent assessment activities by using academic analytics in conjunction with big data and prediction models. The statistical analysis of several data sources may lead to a more efficient application of technology, processes, organisations, and institutional culture. This can be accomplished by analysing the data. The information that may be gained through academic analytics can potentially be used to improve teaching, as well as learning and the results for students. It is possible that a tool of this sort may assist instructors in identifying students who may be struggling academically, allowing such students to get the individualised attention that they need. In order for the higher education system to make effective use of data such as student feedback and statistics, it requires a significant investment of time and effort. Effective operations put a high priority on the elimination of errors and make significant use of enormous amounts of data for the sake of organisation activities; this data often includes student profiles and replies that are required to be provided.

Review Of Literature

The educational industry is one that is seeing significant amounts of both change and competition. Universities and colleges need to make intelligent decisions in order to preserve their position as market leaders. Standard data warehouses in the education sector are exceeding the capabilities of traditional processing approaches for structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data sets by extracting value from non-data sources such as videos, audio, and other non-data sources. This is allowing standard data warehouses to surpass the capabilities of traditional processing approaches for structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data sets. The concept of learning at a distance was first brought up in 1990, although it was not given a clear description at the time. However, the American Society for Training and Development advises against delivering instructional material through electronic devices [2, 3].

The active need for the processing of huge amounts of educational material, which ultimately results in decisions that are based on analysis as opposed to just intuition or experience, is the fundamental obstacle that prevents broad acceptance of e-learning. There are a number of intriguing

applications for large amounts of data in the field of education, including data collected by students, instructors, academic institutions, and so on. The six Vs are a possible framework for defining vast amounts of data (volume, velocity, variety, veracity, value, and volatility). The word "volume" is used to characterise this phenomena since earlier technologies were unable to accommodate the enormous volumes of data handled by big data. The difficulties associated with high-volume data include the collection of data from thousands of students who are enrolled in hundreds of different courses at dozens of different schools. The pace at which information is acquired is what is meant by the term "velocity." Take, for example, the administration of the streaming data generated by a student when they are using a learning management system. Text interactions may be unstructured, semi-structured (such as emails), or structured (such as learner profiles in logical databases). Information can also be unstructured (free text, PDFs, videos, images, web-pages, RSS feeds, Facebook feeds, etc.). When it can be relied upon to be correct and comprehensive, it is said to be valid. The result provides evidence that customers will like the completed product. The degree to which the value of the data fluctuates over time may be measured using a metric called volatility.

Data may be obtained in the subject of education from a wide range of different sources. Data about education may come from a number of places, including academic data sets collected by institutions, data sets that are openly accessible on the internet, and communication data acquired via a range of e-learning platforms. Mobile phones, the internet, other forms of media, and music blogs are examples of potential supplemental resources. Wearable electronics, student attention sensors, and student electrical activity monitoring sensors like NeuroSky head tilt angle for learner engagement assessment are some examples of the types of sensors that are generating useful data on the educational process. Traditional data sets that were obtained via evaluations and course dropout rates are important data sources that need to be handled and examined. The usage of online data sources, such as simulations and instructional games, might potentially give instructive insight into the students. The MOODLE logs are an example of this type of interaction log for a learning environment; they include data such as user ID, the number of times a user has attempted to log in, the total amount of time spent, user clicks, lesson progress, course information, and the date on which course materials were viewed. The health condition of students (including disabilities, illnesses, and medical reports, among other types of information), memory and concentration tests, addresses, and financial

circumstances are only some of the types of personal data that colleges gather and utilise for marketing and other reasons. Information taken directly from the student's own personal history Workshops, extracurricular activities (including things like taking part in contests and seminars), and academic records that are comprehensive, and attendance records. Data that is only relevant to a single classroom, such as how clean the classrooms are or where the school buses are located, might obscure crucial information about the school as a whole that could have an impact on the education of the children.

Discussion

The major focus of the project is on figuring out how to make the most of cloud computing and big data in order to enhance online education. It makes use of on-demand services and robust distributed storage, parallel processing, and real-time analysis technologies in order to better manage large volumes of heterogeneous data and resolve issues with traditional e-learning system components such as suggestion, prediction, and motivation. These issues can arise when traditional e-learning system components are not properly implemented. This section provides an overview of the present status of big data and cloud computing in relation to the field of online education. The work that has been done to blend these three prominent paradigms is examined, and structures, techniques, and use cases are proposed as a result of this examination.

Big Data Into The Online Learning System Framework

This study tackles the introduction of big data into the online learning system by putting up a framework to deliver a learning service of the highest possible quality. This framework makes it easier to include the e-learning industry into the big data ecosystem, which enables both of these industries to take advantage of the most recent advances in data management and analysis. It functions on three different levels simultaneously. The e-learning infrastructure is the initial layer, and it consists of different online tools and resources that may be used for teaching and learning (VCR). This layer also stores information on the learners themselves, such as their profiles, their preferences, and their interactions with the learning system. The second layer is represented by large amounts of data. In point of fact, the information that is obtained from the e-learning platform is passed through this extraction and processing layer in order to get ready, to analyse this information that will be transmitted, later on, to the third layer of results interpretation and data visualisation via a variety of presentation techniques that are offered by particular user applications.

This study demonstrates how the power of big data might be used to assist in resolving a wide variety of issues that are linked with e-learning, hence enhancing the reliability and efficiency of these types of educational platforms. Hadoop, MapReduce, and HDFS are only few of the strong big data approaches and technologies that are used. Additionally, the purpose of this work is to provide some insight on how big data technologies may be used to the investigation of CEHL. A finding suitable educational data source is the first step in these four procedures that need to be taken. Emails, posts on social media, databases used for online learning, and a variety of other digital formats all have the potential to include such information. During the third step, known as "data extraction," information is gathered from a wide variety of sources. When it comes to processing massive amounts of data, the next step is to figure out which programming language and approach would provide the best results for the end user. This can be done by determining which programming language and approach would provide the best results for processing massive amounts of data. The findings of the data analysis are presented in a visual format that is intended to be engaging and straightforward to comprehend as part of the fourth step, which is referred to as data visualisation.

The use of large amounts of data in educational settings is the primary focus of this research endeavour. It presents a framework for merging e-learning technologies with big data methodologies in order to achieve the desired outcomes. To be more specific, the objective is to combine the Learning Management Systems (LMSs) that are now deployed in educational institutions with the Hadoop Framework, which has been developed as a cloud-based SaaS service. Two different approaches are used by Hadoop in order to take benefit of data from a conventional LMS. First things first, the relational database has to be moved from the LMS to the HDFS. The second approach entails copying the information that is neatly organised in an LMS and pasting it into a data warehouse. After the data from the LMS has been included into the Hadoop Framework, it will be feasible to do complicated analyses on the data after having first converted and filtered it. This kind of research has the potential to blaze a trail toward the creation of classrooms that are more flexible and individualised.

The use of big data and cloud computing is becoming more fundamental to the operation of all information systems, including online education platforms. Therefore, integrating them is absolutely necessary in order to reap the benefits of the massive volumes of data generated by such a system, to gain processing and analytical flexibility,

and to be liberated from the difficulties associated with installing the necessary hardware and technical architecture. It is a tough problem to extract valuable information from learning data due to the tremendous growth in the quantity of data collected every day by online learning systems. The big data ecosystem offers cutting-edge tools, methods, and approaches by using machine learning algorithms in the form of highly efficient and user-friendly software libraries. These algorithms are made available through the big data ecosystem (APIs, Frameworks, etc.). These technologies make it easier to gather, clean, and conduct distributed analysis on big datasets, all of which are necessary steps for effective decision-making. They also help e-learning professionals refine and polish their approaches, which allow courses to be personalised to the specific requirements and preferences of each individual student. The first and most fundamental aspect of the strategy that has been presented is the infrastructure. The infrastructure layer is made up of cloud services that can be accessed via virtualization and are used for compute, storage, and networking. E-learning platforms are dependent on the former, and it is the obligation of such platforms to provide the big data technologies and virtual computing resources essential for e-learning platforms to operate effectively. Adjustments may be made as necessary to the resources in this layer. If, for instance, an application needs a lot of processing time or disc space to analyse a massive amount of data, then the architecture of the cloud will automatically grow to disperse these resources among more nodes. This technique offers a lot more discretion than the conventional approach, which is based on the traditional hosting technology. Traditional hosting technology has constraints owing to the restricted availability of server resources, but this strategy eliminates such limitations. The fact that this layer provides a scalable, robust, and error-tolerant infrastructure is the major benefit that it provides.

Conclusion

In any Industry, it is very necessary to have a well-defined methodology in place before beginning the stage of implementation or the stage of operationalization of a project. This technique shows the procedures and checks that are necessary for properly managing projects involving vast amounts of data. In light of this, we need to give some thought to a strategy that may be modified to accommodate the requirements of online education. We are able to do this by identifying important phases in the process of big data that assist educational distance learning in gaining value and insights from the data sources offered by online learning platforms. This requires not only the analysis of the data but also its collection,

preparation, modelling, processing, and presentation. All of these steps must be completed before the data can be analysed. When data is correctly recorded, processed, and evaluated, e-learning professionals are able to get a profound comprehension of their students, the content of their classes, and the outcomes of their assessments. In this approach, they may be able to raise the quality of the curriculum while simultaneously offering students more individualised and tailored educational experiences. A schematization of our methods for using big data in digital classrooms is shown in Figure 3. An in-depth explanation is provided for each of the following aspects of big data: searching and collecting the data, setting it up, modelling it, processing it, and visualising it.

References

1. Benslimane M, Kamar O, Mehdi T, Mohammed B. Proposal of an approach of online course design and implementation: A case study of an algorithmic course. 2016;
2. Dahdouh K, Oughdir L, Dakkak A, Ibriz e A. Smart courses recommender system for online learning platform. In: 2018 IEEE 5th International Congress on Information Science and Technology (CiSt). Marrakech: IEEE; 2018. pp. 328-333. DOI: 10.1109/CIST.2018.8596516
3. Ibriz A. Une Démarche Innovante de Conduite de ProjetElearning: C.D.I.O. In: 2ème Congrès International du Génie Industriel et du Management Des Systèmes (CIGIMS). 2015
4. Larose DT. Data Mining and Predictive Analytics. Hoboken, New Jersey: Published by John Wiley & Sons, Inc.; 2015. p. 827
5. Li H, Yi W, Zhang D, Zhang M, Chang e EY. Pfp: Parallel Fp-growth for query recommendation. In: Proceedings of the 2008 ACM Conference on Recommender Systems—RecSys '08. Lausanne, Switzerland: ACM Press; 2008. p. 107. DOI: 10.1145/1454008.1454027
6. Ouazzani K. Didactics in online learning technical courses: A case study based on activity theory. International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies. 2016;7:849-854
7. Udupi PK, Malali P, Noronha H. Big data integration for transition from E-learning to smart learning framework. In: 2016 3rd MEC International Conference on Big Data and Smart City (ICBDSC). Muscat, Oman: IEEE; 2016. pp. 1-4
8. Wang, K.; Shao, Y.; Shu, L.; Zhu, C.S.; Zhang, Y. Mobile Bid Data Fault-Tolerant Processing for eHealth Networks. IEEE Netw. 2016, 30, 36-42

9. Zhang, G.L.; Sun, J.; Chitkushev, L.; Brusic, V.
Big Data Analytics in Immunology: A
Knowledge-Based Approach. *Biomed. Res. Int.*
2014, 2014, 437987.